

FUNCTIONAL PEARL

Bottom-up computation using trees of sublists: A dependently typed approach

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Abstract

We revisit the problem of implementing a recursion scheme over immediate sublists studied by Mu (2024), and provide a dependently typed solution in Agda. The recursion scheme can be implemented as either a top-down algorithm, which has a straightforward definition but results in lots of re-computation, or a bottom-up algorithm, which has a puzzling definition but avoids re-computation. We show that the types can be made precise to guide and understand the developments of the algorithms. In particular, a precisely typed version of the key data structure (binomial trees) can be derived from the problem specification. The precise types also allow us to prove that the two algorithms are extensionally equal using parametricity. Despite apparent dissimilarities, our proof can be compared to Mu's equational proof, and be understood as a more economical version of Mu's proof.

1 Introduction

The *immediate sublists* of a list xs are those lists obtained by removing exactly one element from xs . For example, the four immediate sublists of "abcd" are "abc", "abd", "acd", and "bcd". Mu (2024) considered the problem of computing a function $h : \text{List } A \rightarrow B$ such that $h\ xs$ depends on values of h at all the immediate sublists of xs .¹ More formally, assuming that the function

$$\text{subs} : \text{List } A \rightarrow \text{List } (\text{List } A)$$

computes the immediate sublists of a list, to compute $h\ xs$ we can decompose xs into $\text{subs } xs : \text{List } (\text{List } A)$, then apply $\text{map } h : \text{List } (\text{List } A) \rightarrow \text{List } B$ recursively to get a list of sub-results for the immediate sublists of xs , and finally invoke a given function $f : \text{List } B \rightarrow B$ to combine the sub-results into a result for xs . That is, h is specified by the equation

$$h\ xs = f (\text{map } h (\text{subs } xs)) \tag{1}$$

The problem is derived from Bird's (2008) study of the relationship between top-down and bottom-up algorithms. Equation (1) expresses a top-down strategy, which, if executed

¹This form of recursive computation arises when, for example, solving an optimisation problem over the permutations of a list and decomposing the problem recursively by considering which element should be the first one in the output permutation. Mu (2024) mentioned some more examples near the end of his Section 1.

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Fig. 1. Computing h "abcd" top-down.

directly, results in lots of re-computation. See Figure 1, for example: h "ab" is computed twice for h "abc" and h "abd", and h "ac" twice for h "abc" and h "acd". A bottom-up strategy that avoids re-computation is shown in Figure 2(a). Values of h on inputs of length n are stored in level n to be reused. Each level $n + 1$ is computed from level n , until we reach the top. One may first attempt to represent each level as a list, but it will turn out that, to build the next level from a current one, we need to maintain more information in the data structure. Bird represented each level using a tip-valued binary tree defined by²

```

data BT (A : Set) : Set where
  tip : A          → BT A
  bin : BT A → BT A → BT A

```

equipped with (overloaded) functions

```

map    : (A → B) → BT A → BT B
zipWith : (A → B → C) → BT A → BT B → BT C

```

respectively the mapping and zipping functions of BT that one would expect. For example, level 2 in Figure 2(a) is represented by the tree in Figure 2(b). Let t be a tree representing level n . To compute level $n + 1$, we need a function $\text{upgrade} : \text{BT } A \rightarrow \text{BT } (\text{List } A)$, a natural transformation copying and rearranging elements in t , such that $\text{map } f$ ($\text{upgrade } t$) represents level $n + 1$. Bird suggested the following definition of upgrade :³

```

upgrade : BT A → BT (List A)
upgrade (bin (tip x) (tip y)) = tip (x :: y :: [])
upgrade (bin t      (tip y)) = bin (upgrade t) (map (λ_ : [ y ]) t)
upgrade (bin (tip x) u      ) = let tip xs = upgrade u in tip (x :: xs)
upgrade (bin t      u      ) = bin (upgrade t) (zipWith λ_ : λ_ t (upgrade u))

```

If you feel puzzled by upgrade , so were we. Being the last example in the paper, Bird did not offer much explanation. The function upgrade is as concise as it is cryptic. The trees appear to obey some shape constraints — Bird called them *binomial trees*, hence the name BT, but neither the constraints nor how upgrade maintains them was explicitly stated.

²We use Agda in this pearl, while both Bird (2008) and Mu (2024) used Haskell; some of their definitions are quoted in this section but translated into Agda notation for consistency.

³This definition of upgrade is translated into Agda notation from Bird's Haskell program; the name upgrade was given by Mu (2024), while the same function was called cd by Bird (2008). To be clear, the definition is not valid Agda: the two sets of patterns at the top level and in the let -expression fail the coverage check; moreover, Agda does not actually allow pattern matching with data constructors in let -expressions.

Fig. 2. (a) Computing $h "abcd"$ bottom-up. (b) Representing level 2 in BT.

Fascinated by Bird’s algorithm, Mu (2024) offered a specification of upgrade and a derivation of the definition, and then proved that the bottom-up algorithm is extensionally equal to the top-down specification/algorithm, all using traditional equational reasoning. As an interlude, Mu also showed (in his Section 4.3) a dependently typed version of upgrade, which used an indexed version of BT that encoded the shape constraint on binomial trees, although Mu did not explore the direction further. In this pearl, we go down the road not (thoroughly) taken and see how far it leads. In a dependently typed setting, can we derive the binomial trees by formalising in their types what we intend to compute? How effectively can the type information help us to implement the top-down and bottom-up algorithms correctly? And does the type information help us to prove that the two algorithms are extensionally equal?

2 The induction principle and its representations

Since we are computing a recursive function $h : \text{List } A \rightarrow B$ given $f : \text{List } B \rightarrow B$, we are dealing with a *recursion scheme* (Yang and Wu 2022) of type

$$(\text{List } B \rightarrow B) \rightarrow \text{List } A \rightarrow B \quad (2)$$

In a dependently typed setting, recursion schemes become *elimination* or *induction principles*, and we will refine type (2) to an induction principle. The first step is refining $\text{List } A \rightarrow B$ to $(xs : \text{List } A) \rightarrow P \text{ } xs$ where $P : \text{List } A \rightarrow \text{Set}$ is the induction *motive* (McBride 2002). And then we should refine the premise $\text{List } B \rightarrow B$ to an induction *method*, whose type states that the motive should be established and preserved in a way that follows the recursive structure of the computation — or more specifically, whenever P holds for all the immediate sublists of a list ys , P should hold for ys as well.

To write down the induction principle formally (in particular the type of the induction method), first we need to define immediate sublists — in fact we will give a more general definition of all sublists, following Mu’s (2024) insight that we will need to refer to all of the sublists during the course of the computation. Recall that an immediate sublist of xs is a list obtained by dropping one element from xs ; more generally, a sublist can be obtained by dropping some number of elements. Element dropping can be written as an inductively defined relation:

```

data DropR : ℕ → List A → List A → Set where
  return : DropR zero xs xs
  drop : DropR n xs ys → DropR (suc n) (x :: xs) ys
  keep : DropR (suc n) xs ys → DropR (suc n) (x :: xs) (x :: ys)

```


205 type classes in Haskell. In effect, the result type M is required to support the usual monoid
 206 operations:

```
207     record Monoid ( $M : \text{Set } \ell$ ) :  $\text{Set } \ell$  where
208         constructor monoid
209         field
210              $\_ \oplus \_ : M \rightarrow M \rightarrow M$ 
211              $\emptyset : M$ 
```

214 With these operations on M , we can implement `mzero` by ignoring the current continuation
 215 and returning \emptyset ,

```
216     mzero : Nondet A
217     mzero =  $\lambda k \rightarrow \emptyset$ 
```

219 and implement `mplus` by running its two branches (both with the current continuation) and
 220 merging the results using the $_ \oplus _$ operation:

```
221     mplus : Nondet A  $\rightarrow$  Nondet A  $\rightarrow$  Nondet A
222     mplus  $mx\ my = \lambda k \rightarrow mx\ k \oplus my\ k$ 
```

225 (Some readers have probably recognised that this is essentially the technique of representing
 226 monads in continuation-passing style (Filinski 1994; Hinze 2012).) If we expand these
 227 definitions in `drop`, we get

```
228     drop :  $\mathbb{N} \rightarrow \text{List } A \rightarrow \{\{ \text{Monoid } M \}\} \rightarrow (\text{List } A \rightarrow M) \rightarrow M$ 
229     drop zero  $xs\ k = k\ xs$ 
230     drop (suc  $n$ ) []  $k = \emptyset$ 
231     drop (suc  $n$ ) ( $x :: xs$ )  $k = \text{drop } n\ xs\ k \oplus \text{drop } (\text{buc } n)\ xs\ (k \circ (x :: \_))$ 
```

234 which we can instantiate to various forms. For example, we can instantiate `drop` to compute
 235 all the sublists of a particular length, supplying the list monoid as the result type:

```
236     dropL :  $\mathbb{N} \rightarrow \text{List } A \rightarrow \text{List } (\text{List } A)$ 
237     dropL  $n\ xs = \text{drop } n\ xs\ \{\{ \text{monoid } \_ \# \_ [] \}\} (\_ :: [])$ 
```

239 In particular, `subs = dropL 1` computes immediate sublists.

240 More importantly, we want to instantiate `drop` to compute types. For example, `DropR` can
 241 alternatively be defined in continuation-passing style by

```
242     DropR  $n\ xs\ ys \cong \text{drop } n\ xs\ \{\{ \text{monoid } \_ \uplus \_ \perp \}\} (\_ \equiv ys)$ 
```

244 where `drop $n\ xs\ \{\{ \text{monoid } _ \uplus _ \perp \}\} : (\text{List } A \rightarrow \text{Set}) \rightarrow \text{Set}$` amounts to existential
 245 quantification over sublists: an input predicate $P : \text{List } A \rightarrow \text{Set}$ is only required to hold
 246 in one of the branches at every nondeterministic choice (since we instantiate the monoid
 247 operation $_ \oplus _$ to disjunction $_ \uplus _$), so eventually P is only required to hold for one sublist.
 248 To obtain universal quantification, we supply the conjunction `monoid $_ \times _ \top$` , requiring P to
 249 hold for all the branches and thus all the sublists:

```
250     Drop  $n\ P\ xs \cong \text{drop } n\ xs\ \{\{ \text{monoid } \_ \times \_ \top \}\} P$ 
```

253 Rewriting the function definition as a data type definition (by turning each clause into a
 254 constructor), we get

255

```

256 data Drop :  $\mathbb{N} \rightarrow (\text{List } A \rightarrow \text{Set}) \rightarrow \text{List } A \rightarrow \text{Set}$  where
257   tip :  $P \text{ } xs$   $\rightarrow \text{Drop } \mathbf{zero} \ P \text{ } xs$ 
258   nil :  $\text{Drop } (\mathbf{suc } n) \ P \ []$ 
259   bin :  $\text{Drop } n \ P \text{ } xs \rightarrow \text{Drop } (\mathbf{suc } n) \ (P \circ (x :: \_)) \text{ } xs \rightarrow \text{Drop } (\mathbf{suc } n) \ P \ (x :: xs)$ 
260

```

which we will use to represent the induction hypotheses in the induction principle:

```

261 ImmediateSublistInduction :  $\text{Set}_1$ 
262 ImmediateSublistInduction =  $\{A : \text{Set}\} (P : \text{List } A \rightarrow \text{Set})$ 
263  $(f : \forall \{ys\} \rightarrow \text{Drop } 1 \ P \ ys \rightarrow P \ ys)$ 
264  $(xs : \text{List } A) \rightarrow P \ xs$ 
265
266
267

```

Comparing ImmediateSublistInduction with type (2), a potentially drastic change is that the *list* of induction hypotheses is replaced with a *tree* of type $\text{Drop } 1 \ P \ ys$ here. However, such a tree is actually list-shaped (constructed using **nil** and **bin** \circ **tip**), so ImmediateSublistInduction is a faithful refinement of type (2). Moreover, we will see that Drop is a refinement of BT (Section 1) with an additional **nil** constructor — we will reimplement the upgrade function used in the bottom-up algorithm to operate on Drop trees, and the same computation patterns will emerge. The refinement from BT to Drop gives us a better idea of why Bird (2008) needed to use BT: paths in BT/Drop trees correspond to computation of sublists of a particular length, so working with BT/Drop trees allows us to figure out which sublist each element in the trees is associated with and put the elements at the right places; the associations are only implicitly assumed in BT, whereas in Drop they are explicitly recorded in the element types of the form $P \ xs$.

In Sections 3 and 4 we will implement the top-down and bottom-up algorithms as programs of type ImmediateSublistInduction. These are fairly standard exercises in dependently typed programming (except perhaps for upgrade), and our implementations are by no means the only solutions.⁵ The reader may want to try the exercises for themselves, and is not obliged to go through the details of our programs. We will prove that the two algorithms are extensionally equal in Section 5; the proof will not depend on the implementation details of the two algorithms, but only on their shared dependent type.

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290

3 The top-down algorithm

Equation (1) is essentially an executable definition of the top-down algorithm. This definition would not pass Agda's termination check though, because the immediate sublists in $\text{subs } xs$ would not be recognised as structurally smaller than xs . One way to make termination evident is to make the length of xs explicit and perform induction on the length. The following function `td` does this by invoking `td'`, which takes as additional arguments a natural number l and an equality proof stating that the length of xs is l . The function `td'` then performs induction on l and does the real work.

```

291 td : ImmediateSublistInduction
292 td  $\{A\} \ P \ f \text{ } xs = \text{td}' \ (\text{length } xs) \text{ } xs \ \mathbf{refl}$ 
293
294 where -- lenSubs to be defined later
295   td' :  $(l : \mathbb{N}) (xs : \text{List } A) \rightarrow \text{length } xs \equiv l \rightarrow P \ xs$ 
296
297
298

```

304
305
306

⁵Even the induction principle has alternative formulations, one of which was explored by Ko et al. (2025).

307 $\text{td}' \text{ zero } [] \text{ eq} = f \text{ nil}$
 308 $\text{td}' (\text{succ } l) \text{ xs eq} = f (\text{map } (\lambda \{ys\} \rightarrow \text{td}' l \text{ ys}) (\text{lenSubs } l \text{ xs eq}))$

309
 310 In the first case of td' , where xs is $[]$, the final result is simply $f \text{ nil} : P []$. In the second
 311 case of td' , where the length of xs is $\text{succ } l$, the function subs is adapted to lenSubs , which
 312 constructs equality proofs that all the immediate sublists of xs have length l :

313 $\text{lenSubs} : (l : \mathbb{N}) (\text{xs} : \text{List } A) \rightarrow \text{length } \text{xs} \equiv \text{succ } l$
 314 $\rightarrow \text{Drop } 1 (\lambda \text{ys} \rightarrow \text{length } \text{ys} \equiv l) \text{ xs}$

316 With these equality proofs, we can then invoke td' inductively on every immediate sublist of
 317 xs with the help of the map function for Drop ,
 318

319 $\text{map} : (\forall \{ys\} \rightarrow P \text{ys} \rightarrow Q \text{ys}) \rightarrow \text{Drop } n P \text{xs} \rightarrow \text{Drop } n Q \text{xs}$

320 and again use f to compute the final result.
 321

322

323

4 The bottom-up algorithm

324

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332

$\text{base} : (\text{xs} : \text{List } A) \rightarrow \text{Drop } (\text{succ } (\text{length } \text{xs})) P \text{xs}$

333

334

335

336

$\text{bu} : \text{ImmediateSublistInduction}$

337

$\text{bu } P f = \text{bu}' _ \circ \text{base}$

338

where -- unTip and retabulate to be defined later

339

$\text{bu}' : (n : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{Drop } n P \text{xs} \rightarrow P \text{xs}$

340

$\text{bu}' \text{ zero} = \text{unTip}$

341

$\text{bu}' (\text{succ } n) = \text{bu}' n \circ \text{map } f \circ \text{retabulate}$

342

343

344

345

When the loop counter reaches zero , the tree contains exactly the result for xs , which we can extract using

346

$\text{unTip} : \text{Drop } \text{zero } P \text{xs} \rightarrow P \text{xs}$

347

$\text{unTip } (\text{tip } p) = p$

348

349

350

351

352

353

354

355

If the loop counter is $\text{succ } n$, we create a new tree of type $\text{Drop } n P \text{xs}$ that is one level higher than the current tree of type $\text{Drop } (\text{succ } n) P \text{xs}$. The type of the new tree says that it should contain results of type $P \text{ys}$ for all the sublists ys at the higher level. The retabulate function, which plays the same role as upgrade (Section 1), does half of the work by copying and rearranging the elements of the current tree to construct an intermediate tree representing the higher level:

356

$\text{retabulate} : \text{Drop } (\text{succ } n) P \text{xs} \rightarrow \text{Drop } n (\text{Drop } 1 P) \text{xs}$

357

358 It assembles for each ys the induction hypotheses needed for computing $P\ ys$ using f — that
 359 is, each element of the intermediate tree is a tree of type $\text{Drop } 1\ P\ ys$. Then $\text{map } f$ does the
 360 rest of the work and produces the desired new tree of type $\text{Drop } n\ P\ xs$, and we enter the next
 361 iteration.

362 To implement `retabulate`, follow the types, and most of the program writes itself. We will
 363 not go through the construction of the program in detail because we only aim to show the
 364 correctness of `bu`, which depends only on the type of `retabulate`.
 365

```

366   retabulate : Drop (suc n) P xs → Drop n (Drop 1 P) xs
367   retabulate  nil                = underground
368   retabulate t@(bin (tip _ ) _ ) = tip t
369   retabulate (bin nil nil)      = bin underground nil
370   retabulate (bin t@(bin _ _ ) u) = bin (retabulate t)
371                                     (zipWith (bin ∘ tip) t (retabulate u))
372
373
374

```

374 The auxiliary function `underground` is defined by

```

375
376   underground : Drop n (Drop 1 P) []
377   underground {n = zero } = tip nil
378   underground {n = suc _ } = nil
379
380

```

381 (It analyses the implicit argument n , which therefore needs to be present at runtime, so
 382 `retabulate` actually requires more information than the input tree to execute, unlike `upgrade`.)
 383 The last clause of `retabulate` is the most difficult one to conceive, but can be copied exactly
 384 from the last clause of `upgrade` except that the list `cons` is replaced by the `cons` function
 385 $\text{bin} \circ \text{tip}$ for $\text{Drop } 1$ trees (which, as mentioned near the end of Section 2, are list-shaped),
 386 and the type of `zipWith` needs to be updated:
 387

```

388   zipWith : (∀ {ys} → P ys → Q ys → R ys)
389             → Drop n P xs → Drop n Q xs → Drop n R xs
390

```

391 It is a fruitful exercise to trace the constraints assumed and established throughout the
 392 construction (especially the last clause), which are now manifested as type information —
 393 see [Ko et al.'s \(2025\) Section 2.3](#) for a solution to a similar version of the exercise.
 394

395 The first and third clauses of `retabulate` involve `nil`, and have no counterparts in `upgrade`.
 396 Drop trees containing `nil` correspond to empty levels below the lattice in Figure 2(a) (which
 397 result from dropping too many elements from the input list). [Mu \(2024\)](#) avoided dealing with
 398 such empty levels by imposing conditions throughout his development — for example, see
 399 [Mu's Section 4.3](#) and [Appendix B](#) for a version of the program (which is named up there)
 400 with conditions. We avoid those somewhat tedious conditions by including `nil` in Drop to
 401 represent the empty levels, and in exchange need to deal with these levels, which are easier to
 402 deal with than the conditions though.
 403

404 5 Extensional equality between the two algorithms

405 Now we have two different implementations of `ImmediateSublistInduction`, namely `td` and
 406 `bu`. How do we prove that they compute the same results?
 407
 408

409 Actually, is it possible to write programs of type `ImmediateSublistInduction` to compute
 410 different results in Agda? It may help to consider a simpler example: induction on natural
 411 numbers,

```
412  $\mathbb{N}$ Induction : Set1
413  $\mathbb{N}$ Induction = (P :  $\mathbb{N} \rightarrow \text{Set}$ )
414               (pz : P zero) (ps :  $\forall \{n\} \rightarrow P n \rightarrow P (\text{succ } n)$ )
415               (n :  $\mathbb{N}$ )  $\rightarrow P n$ 
```

416 which has a standard implementation:

```
417
418
419 ind $\mathbb{N}$  :  $\mathbb{N}$ Induction
420 ind $\mathbb{N}$  P pz ps zero = pz
421 ind $\mathbb{N}$  P pz ps (succ n) = ps (ind $\mathbb{N}$  P pz ps n)
```

422 There are other implementations of `\mathbb{N} Induction` (a tail-recursive one, for example). But
 423 since `\mathbb{N} Induction` is parametric in P , on which the only given operations are pz and ps , any
 424 implementation can only compute a result of type $P n$ using pz and ps ; moreover, the index n
 425 determines that result — it has to be n applications of ps to pz . For `ImmediateSublistInduction`
 426 we can reason similarly, and conclude that `td` and `bu` have to compute the same results simply
 427 because they have the same —and special— type!

428 To prove this formally, we use parametricity, first for the simpler `\mathbb{N} Induction`. The following
 429 is the unary parametricity statement of `\mathbb{N} Induction` derived using [Bernardy et al.’s \(2012\)](#)
 430 translation, which is a predicate on programs of type `\mathbb{N} Induction`:

```
431  $\mathbb{N}$ InductionUnaryParametricity :  $\mathbb{N}$ Induction  $\rightarrow$  Set1
432  $\mathbb{N}$ InductionUnaryParametricity ind =
433   {P :  $\mathbb{N} \rightarrow \text{Set}$ }           (Q :  $\forall \{n\} \rightarrow P n \rightarrow \text{Set}$ )
434   {pz : P zero}                 (qz : Q pz)
435   {ps :  $\forall \{n\} \rightarrow P n \rightarrow P (\text{succ } n)$ } (qs :  $\forall \{n\} \{p : P n\} \rightarrow Q p \rightarrow Q (ps p)$ )
436   {n :  $\mathbb{N}$ }                        $\rightarrow Q (\text{ind } P \text{ pz } ps n)$ 
```

437 (The typesetting helps to distinguish the original arguments in `\mathbb{N} Induction` on the left column
 438 from the entities introduced by the parametricity translation on the right.) Unary parametricity
 439 can be understood in terms of invariant preservation: state an invariant Q on values of type of
 440 the form $P n$, prove (by supplying qz and qs) that Q is satisfied by pz and preserved by ps ,
 441 and then the results computed by `ind P pz ps` will satisfy Q (intuitively because `ind` can only
 442 construct its result using pz and ps). Given a program `ind : \mathbb{N} Induction`, we can obtain a
 443 proof of its unary parametricity for free,

```
444
445
446 param :  $\mathbb{N}$ InductionUnaryParametricity ind
```

447 for example using [Bernardy et al.’s translation](#) again or internal parametricity ([Van Muylder](#)
 448 [et al. 2024](#)). For any P , pz , and ps , we invoke the parametricity proof with the invariant

```
449
450
451  $\lambda \{n\} p \rightarrow p \equiv \text{ind } \mathbb{N} P pz ps n : \forall \{n\} \rightarrow P n \rightarrow \text{Set}$ 
```

452 saying that any $p : P n$ can only be the result computed by `ind \mathbb{N} P pz ps n` (that is,
 453 n applications of ps to pz). This invariant can be easily proved to hold for pz and be preserved
 454 by ps , so we get a proof that `ind` has to be extensionally equal to `ind \mathbb{N}` :

460 $param (\lambda \{n\} p \rightarrow p \equiv ind \mathbb{N} P pz ps n) \mathbf{refl} (\lambda \{\mathbf{refl} \rightarrow \mathbf{refl}\})$
 461 $: \{n : \mathbb{N}\} \rightarrow ind P pz ps n \equiv ind \mathbb{N} P pz ps n$

462 The proof can be readily adapted for ImmediateSublistInduction. The unary parametricity
 463 statement with respect to P (whereas A is treated merely as a fixed parameter) is
 464

465 UnaryParametricity : ImmediateSublistInduction \rightarrow Set₁
 466 UnaryParametricity *ind* =
 467 $\{A : \text{Set}\}$
 468 $\{P : \text{List } A \rightarrow \text{Set}\} \quad (Q : \forall \{ys\} \rightarrow P \text{ } ys \rightarrow \text{Set})$
 469 $\{f : \forall \{ys\} \rightarrow \text{Drop } 1 P \text{ } ys \rightarrow P \text{ } ys\} \quad (g : \forall \{ys\} \{ps : \text{Drop } 1 P \text{ } ys\}$
 470 $\rightarrow \text{All } Q \text{ } ps \rightarrow Q (f \text{ } ps))$
 471 $\rightarrow \text{All } Q \text{ } ps \rightarrow Q (f \text{ } ps))$
 472 $\{xs : \text{List } A\} \quad \rightarrow Q (ind P f xs)$
 473

474 In the type of g , we need an auxiliary definition to formulate the premise that Q is satisfied
 475 by all the elements in a Drop tree:

476 All : $(\forall \{ys\} \rightarrow P \text{ } ys \rightarrow \text{Set}) \rightarrow \text{Drop } n P \text{ } xs \rightarrow \text{Set}$
 477 All Q (**tip** p) = $Q \text{ } p$
 478 All Q **nil** = \top
 479 All Q (**bin** $t u$) = All $Q \text{ } t \times$ All $Q \text{ } u$
 480

481 Then a proof of the extensional equality between *td* and *bu* can be obtained similarly from a
 482 parametricity proof *buParam* : UnaryParametricity *bu*.
 483

484 *buParam* $(\lambda \{ys\} p \rightarrow \text{td } P f \text{ } ys \equiv p) \text{tdComp} : \forall \{xs\} \rightarrow \text{td } P f \text{ } xs \equiv \text{bu } P f \text{ } xs$ (4)
 485

486 The argument *tdComp* proving that f preserves the invariant is worth taking a closer look.
 487 Its type is

488 $\forall \{ys\} \{ps : \text{Drop } 1 P \text{ } ys\} \rightarrow \text{All} (\lambda \{zs\} p \rightarrow \text{td } P f \text{ } zs \equiv p) \text{ } ps \rightarrow \text{td } P f \text{ } ys \equiv f \text{ } ps$
 489

490 which says that computing $\text{td } P f \text{ } ys$ is the same as applying f to ps where every p in ps is
 491 already a result computed by $\text{td } P f$ — this has the same computational content as equation (1),
 492 and is a formulation of the *computation rule* of ImmediateSublistInduction, satisfied by
 493 *td!* (That is, computation rules can be formulated as a form of invariant preservation.)
 494 Incidentally, this explains why it was easy to discharge similar proof obligations in the proof
 495 for \mathbb{N} Induction: $ind \mathbb{N}$ satisfies the computation rules of \mathbb{N} Induction definitionally.
 496

497 Therefore, behind equality (4) is a theorem with a bit more structure and generality. If we
 498 formulate the computation rule for any implementation *ind* of ImmediateSublistInduction,

499 ComputationRule : ImmediateSublistInduction \rightarrow Set₁
 500 ComputationRule *ind* =
 501 $\{A : \text{Set}\} \{P : \text{List } A \rightarrow \text{Set}\} \{f : \forall \{ys\} \rightarrow \text{Drop } 1 P \text{ } ys \rightarrow P \text{ } ys\} \{xs : \text{List } A\}$
 502 $\{ps : \text{Drop } 1 P \text{ } xs\} \rightarrow \text{All} (\lambda \{ys\} p \rightarrow ind P f \text{ } ys \equiv p) \text{ } ps \rightarrow ind P f \text{ } xs \equiv f \text{ } ps$
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504 then we can generalise equality (4) to a theorem that equates the extensional behaviour of
 505 any two implementations of the induction principle, where one implementation satisfies the
 506 computation rule and the other satisfies unary parametricity:
 507

508 uniqueness :
 509 $(ind \text{ } ind' : \text{ImmediateSublistInduction})$
 510

511 \rightarrow ComputationRule $ind \rightarrow$ UnaryParametricity ind'
 512 $\rightarrow \{A : \text{Set}\} (P : \text{List } A \rightarrow \text{Set}) (f : \forall \{ys\} \rightarrow \text{Drop } 1 P \text{ } ys \rightarrow P \text{ } ys) (xs : \text{List } A)$
 513 $\rightarrow ind P f xs \equiv ind' P f xs$
 514 uniqueness $ind _ comp param' P f _ = param' (\lambda \{ys\} p \rightarrow ind P f ys \equiv p) comp$
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6 Methodological discussions

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6.1 Proving uniqueness of induction principle implementations from parametricity

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Usually, we prove two implementations ind and ind' of an induction principle to be equal assuming that both ind and ind' satisfy the set of computation rules coming with the induction principle. For example, for ImmediateSublistInduction we can prove

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$(ind \ ind' : \text{ImmediateSublistInduction})$
 \rightarrow ComputationRule $ind \rightarrow$ ComputationRule ind'
 $\rightarrow \{A : \text{Set}\} (P : \text{List } A \rightarrow \text{Set}) (f : \forall \{ys\} \rightarrow \text{Drop } 1 P \text{ } ys \rightarrow P \text{ } ys) (xs : \text{List } A)$
 $\rightarrow ind P f xs \equiv ind' P f xs$

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The uniqueness theorem in Section 5 demonstrates (in terms of ImmediateSublistInduction) that we can alternatively assume that one implementation, say ind' , satisfies unary parametricity instead, and we will still have a proof. This is useful when ind can be easily proved to satisfy the set of computation rules whereas ind' cannot. In our case, even though our td in Section 3 does not satisfy the computation rule definitionally (because it performs a different form of induction on the length of the input list, to make termination evident to Agda), a proof of ComputationRule td still takes only a small amount of work. It would be more difficult to prove that bu satisfies the computation rule, whereas a parametricity proof for bu is always mechanical —if not automatic— to derive, so switching to the latter greatly reduces the proof burden. In general, this trick may be useful for porting recursion schemes or inventing efficient implementations of induction principles in a dependently typed setting.

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6.2 Establishing invariants using indexed data types and parametricity

Mu (2024) took pains to prove that the two algorithms are extensionally equal, whereas in this pearl the equality seems to follow almost for free from parametricity. The trick is that the necessary properties are either enforced by types or established by parametricity. Recall that in Section 1 the top-down algorithm is computed by $h : \text{List } A \rightarrow B$ given $f : \text{List } B \rightarrow B$. The main property Mu needed was his Lemma 1, which can be roughly translated into our setting as

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$$(\text{map } f \circ \text{upgrade})^k (\text{base}' \text{ } xs) = \text{map } h (\text{drop}^{\text{BT}} (\text{succ } (\text{length } xs) - k) \text{ } xs) \quad (5)$$

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This is an old-school way of saying that the bottom-up algorithm maintains an invariant. The left-hand side is the value computed by the bottom-up algorithm after k iterations: xs is the initial input; base' plays a similar role as base in Section 4 and prepares an initial tree, on which $\text{map } f \circ \text{upgrade}$, the loop body of the bottom-up algorithm, is performed k times. The invariant is that the value must equal the right-hand side: a tree containing values $h \text{ } ys$ for all the sublists ys of xs having k elements — that is, those sublists obtained by dropping $\text{succ } (\text{length } xs) - k$ elements from xs ; this tree has the same shape as the one built by $\text{drop}^{\text{BT}} : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \text{List } A \rightarrow \text{BT } (\text{List } A)$, which also determines the position of each $h \text{ } ys$ in

the tree. By contrast, this pearl uses (i) the indexed data type `Drop` to enforce tree shapes and sublist positions and (ii) parametricity to establish that the trees contain values of `td`.

Using indexed data types to enforce shape constraints is a well known technique, which in particular was briefly employed by [Mu \(2024, Section 4.3\)](#). But program specifications are often not just about shapes. For example, to prove equation (5), Mu gave a specification of `upgrade`:

$$\text{upgrade } (\text{drop}^{\text{BT}} (\mathbf{succ} \ k) \ xs) = \text{map subs } (\text{drop}^{\text{BT}} \ k \ xs)$$

from which the derivation of `upgrade`'s definition was the main challenge for Mu. Shape-wise, this equation says that given a tree having the shape computed by `dropBT (succ k) xs`, `upgrade` produces a tree having the shape computed by `dropBT k xs`. But the equation also specifies how the natural transformation should rearrange the tree elements by saying what it should do in particular to the trees of sublists computed by `dropBT (succ k) xs`. This pearl demonstrates that it is possible to go beyond shapes and encode the full specification in the type of `retabulate` (Section 4) using the indexed data type `Drop`. The key is that the element types in `Drop` trees are indexed by sublists and therefore distinct in general, so the elements need to be placed at the right positions to be type-correct. Subsequently, the definition of `retabulate` can be developed in a type-driven manner, which is more economical than Mu's equational derivation since the type checker takes over a large part of the work.

Equation (5) also says that each iteration of the bottom-up algorithm produces the same results as those computed by `h`, and [Mu \(2024\)](#) proved equation (5) by induction on `k`. What is the relationship between Mu's inductive proof and ours based on `UnaryParametricity bu` (Section 5)? Mu's induction on `k` coincides with the looping structure of the bottom-up algorithm. On the other hand, while `UnaryParametricity` could in principle be proved mechanically once-and-for-all for all functions having the right type, if one had to prove `UnaryParametricity bu` manually, the proof would also follow the structure of `bu`. Therefore the proof of `bu`'s unary parametricity would essentially be the proof of equation (5) generalised to all invariants. Then the uniqueness proof only needs to plug in the key part of the proof (namely the preservation of our chosen invariant) and does not need to go through the definition of `bu`. Finally, note that this opportunity to invoke parametricity emerges because we switch to dependent types and reformulate the recursion scheme as an induction principle: knowing that a result `p` has the indexed type `P ys` allows us to state the invariant $Q \{ys\} p = \text{td } P f \ ys \equiv p$, whereas the non-indexed result type `B` in type (2) does not provide enough information for stating that.

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Zhixuan Yang engaged in several discussions about induction principles, computation rules, and parametricity, leading to the current presentation of the parametricity-based proof. He also pointed out how `Nondet` is an instance of the codensity representation except that a dinaturality condition is omitted ([Hinze 2012](#)). At the IFIP WG 2.1 meeting in April 2024, James McKinna suggested defining `retabulate` on the higher-order representation (3) instead. This definition of `retabulate` is extremely simple, but does not copy and reuse results on sublists, and therefore does not help to avoid re-computation. However, this perspective does make the relationship between binomial trees and proofs of universal quantification clear, and leads to the inclusion of the `nil` constructor in `Drop` (which helps to simplify our definition of `retabulate`). At the same meeting, Wouter Swierstra asked whether lists could be used instead

of vectors in a previous definition of binomial trees (Ko et al. 2025). There the definition of immediate sublists depends on the length of the input list, so it is more convenient to use vectors. However, this question leads us to consider a definition of immediate sublists that does not depend on list length, and ultimately to the simpler definition of Drop (which uses lists instead of vectors). Yen-Hao Liu previewed and provided feedback on a draft. The anonymous reviewers also provided valuable feedback for us to make the presentation more accessible. We would like to thank all of them.

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